

Study of Values of Working and Non-working Women

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Abstract

The present study AIMS at finding the impact of employment of women on different values 60 females(30 working and 30 non working females) were administered with the study of values questionnaire by RK Ojha (1977). Significance of mean difference was tested by applying 't' test. Findings reveal that there is no significant difference in various values of employed or unemployed women. Employment had no impact upon various values of women, suggesting that values being a personality trait do not interplay with situational variables.

Keywords Values, Working, Non-working, Women.

Introduction

Values are individual beliefs that motivate people to act one way or another. They serve as a guide for human behaviour they help us to be authentic and conduct ourselves properly in a variety of social settings that differ from short term or long term goals because they are not specific to a single situation. In the rapidly changing society nowadays women's needs and attitudes are also changing. Working women may be defined as those women who are earning full or part of their livelihood by engaging themselves in any occupation or work for pay or profit. Non-working women are confined to the house and are economically dependent on the elders of the family such as father, husband and brothers etc.

Aim of study

The main objective of the present study was to find out the difference in various values of working and non-working women.

Review of Literature

Classification of values (Spranger, 1928) reflects personality. Some Indian studies (Juneja 1979 ; Bose 1985) have compared the child-rearing attitudes of employed and non-employed mothers. The result reveals that working mothers are less dominant, aggressive and suppressive to their children as compared to the non-working mothers. It was assumed that there would be greater scores on social, economic and political values of working females than on non-working females.

Indian women who wish to get recognition and satisfaction in their career outside the home may often find it difficult to get mental peace due to the overburden of work and may presume themselves as self-fulfilled. Lack of evidence regarding religious values difference of employed women leads to the hypothesis that the degree of expressed religious values would differ in employed and unemployed women. Feminine characteristics of personality, beauty and harmony are inborn traits of females.

But contrary to the notion a clear regional gap in work values was found by women of East Germany and West Germany which was attributed to the effect of Pre-unification differences in state ideology (Adler and Brayfield, 1997)

Perception of family environment may affect women's needs, values and work preferences. Women who experienced the family environment as oriented towards competitive political and cultural activities as open to expression of feelings and as having set rules and procedures were satisfied with their jobs (Sinacore-Guinn, et al., 1999)

- Hypothesis**
1. There will be no difference in aesthetic value of both the groups.
 2. There will be greater scores on theoretical, social, economic and political values of working female than those of non working females.
 3. Non working females would score higher on the religious value than working females.

Methodology

The sample was subjected individually for administration and scoring of values test. In order to compare value pattern on working and non working women t test was applied.

Sampling

The sample undertaken for the study was a purposive sample. A total of 60 women (30 working and 30 non-working) between the age of 25 to 45 years were studied. Working remains group constituted of those women who went out for earning in various agencies of occupation such as advocates, scientists, doctors, teachers, clerks etc. non working women were housewives of the same age group.

Tools Used

'Study of values' in hindi developed by R K Ojha (1977) was used for the purpose. The test measures six types of values namely; theoretical, economical, aesthetic, social, political and religious.

Result and Discussion

The statistical analysis of data showed that there is no significant difference between working and non-working women on any of the values. This shows that value is a personality variable which does not interplay with situational variable, therefore woman whether working or non-working do not show any difference on this dimension. Hypothesis proposed for aesthetic value is accepted. It shows that all women have seen sense of beauty and harmony whether they live in the house or go outside for work. As assumed, greater scores were obtained by working women only on theoretical value but not on economical, social and political values. It is therefore inferred that intelligence and wisdom are inborn characteristics of females and they solve problems by logical thinking. Both the groups showed desire of economic protection by elders.

Conclusion

Other personality traits of sympathy, friendliness, devotion, faith in God were also not found different in both the groups. Study has revealed that over time, values do not change markedly but discrepancy emerged between preference and expectations of working and non-working females (Davay and Heather, 1998).

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